

The profile of selected communities in Maragondon, Cavite: A basis for enhancement of a five-year development plan

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Abstract

This study surveyed the needs of Barangays Talipusngo and Layong Mabilog, in Maragondon, Cavite, as sites for possible adopted communities of St. Dominic College of Asia for outreach and extension services. The study involved 69 respondents from Talipusngo and 71 from Layong Mabilog, who represented 30% of the households in the community. The respondents were selected by quota sampling since the researchers only included household members who were available for the survey and interview. Barangays Talipusngo and Layong Mabilog comprise households that are mostly nuclear and are composed of families with more than three or four children each. In addition, in terms of authority, most are patriarchal. The majority of the residents had been in their respective barangays for more than 26 years. Most of the community members only acquired basic education, and most families are considered poor considering their small income. Moreover, the majority owned their houses, which were mostly made of concrete or mixed (concrete-wood) materials. They have health center facilities that are fully utilized for maternal and child care. Most of the members of the community in both barangays have their own individual water supply connections. In Talipusngo, the majority disposed of their garbage by burning, while in Layong Mabilog, they segregated and recycled their solid waste. For sewerage and waste water disposal, the majority used pit latrine types. They are aware of the existence of an organization, and they are involved. Communication is not a problem since almost all were given by the respondents, with cellular phones being their major communication gadgets. As to their family status for the last five years, they claimed that their status is the same as usual, meaning the status quo. Members of the community identified food as their primary need, followed by financial needs, education, health, and clothing. Family-related problems are mostly financial in nature. Community-related problems include garbage, roads, and water systems, including insects, pests, and animals. An extensive outreach program has to be developed by the institution as an offshoot of the community needs survey to include the findings of the study.

Keywords: Profile; Adopted communities; Barangay Talipusngo; Barangay Layong Mabilog; Enhancement.

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Introduction

The Higher Education Act of 1994, also known as Republic Act 7722, requires private and state universities and colleges (SUCs), among other higher education institutions, to address calls for societal change. This legal requirement is administered by the Commission on Higher Education. Serving the most disadvantaged as well as the underprivileged, deprived, and oppressed is the goal of most of the higher education institutions in the Philippines. Educational institutions then put up various extension programs and services for their adopted communities, including livelihood assistance, the provision of basic health needs, the attainment or improvement of literacy, and the and the attainment of a safe and clean environment, among others.

Bidad and Campiseño (2010) asserted that the majority of extension programs at private and state universities and colleges (SUCs) are driven by accreditation and demand. Demand-driven development is locally based and involves essential needs as well as demands aimed at establishing and improving the overall well-being of people in both urban and rural areas. The relevant local government units usually make this request after determining the particular needs of their citizens. According to Bever et al. (2021), there are other ways of integrating health into decision-making beyond health impact evaluations. These mechanisms include official and informal agreements between agencies, statutory requirements, and voluntary efforts. The latter is especially crucial for individuals residing in rural regions.

However, accreditation-driven extension programs have been put in place in response to demands made by an accrediting agency. Even if they were created in distinct ways, the implementation enhances the institution's course offerings. The St. Dominic College of Asia's Community Extension Services Office (SDCA-CESO) aims to establish its own extension unit with similar objectives. Above all, students and employees will be able to share their knowledge and resources with the underprivileged residents of Maragondon through its outreach and extension programs and services (Tomines, 2021).

The goal of St. Dominic College of Asia's community outreach initiatives has always been to assist those in need and promote to administrators, teachers, staff, and students the importance of volunteer work. It is committed to applying the knowledge, abilities, and values learned in the classroom into practice and generating a passion for serving the Dominican community by learning about, living, and experiencing the lives of the socially underprivileged groups (Tomines, 2021).

In the past years, the SDCA's adopted barangay in Bacoor, Cavite, Barangay Digman, in collaboration with the different schools and departments, provided literacy and social services to the community, including teachers and pupils. This institution wants to provide more services to the other areas in Maragondon, Cavite.

The Community Extension Services Office chose Barangays Talipusngo and Layong Mabilog as locations for outreach and extension services to be provided to community members, teachers, and primary school students after adequate collaboration with the municipality of Maragondon. To be able to put up viable and sustainable outreach and extension programs, the community outreach coordinator, together with the faculty, staff, and student volunteers, went to survey the communities, and the findings are discussed in this study.

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to assess the needs of Barangays Talipusngo and Layong Mabilog communities and subsequently develop a community based program for them. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. describe Barangays Talipusngo and Layong Mabilog community along:
 - a. family structure
 - b. length of residency
 - c. socio-economic profile
 - d. home and environment profile
 - e. health profile
2. identify the existing conditions of the community residents;
3. identify the needs of the community residents;
4. identify the family and community problems of Barangays Talipusngo and Layong Mabilog; and
5. propose an outreach and extension program based on the needs of the community.

Methodology

The study used the descriptive method, which identified the needs of the Barangays Talipusngo and Layong Mabilog communities in Maragondon, Cavite, using a structured survey instrument as the primary data gathering tool. The researchers used community profiling to assess the status of households in the abovementioned barangays. Community profiling can be used to determine the health priorities of the people involved in the community and to consider decision-making processes that would reduce such inequalities (Jack & Holt, 2008).

The data collected was further substantiated by interviews. The study involved 69 respondents from Barangay Talipusngo and 71 respondents from Barangay Layong Mabilog, who represented 30% of the households in the community. The respondents were selected by quota sampling since the researchers only included household members who were free for the survey and the interview. Informed consent was given to the respondents, given that voluntary participation has been involved in the different households. Frequency and percentage distribution were used to determine the status of the profiles of the households within Barangays Talipusngo and Layong Mabilog.

Results and Discussion

1. Community Profile

The communities of Barangays Talipusngo and Layong Mabilog were described along family structure, length of residency, socio-economic and cultural, home and environment, and health profiles.

1.1. Family Structure

The family structure in this study refers to the type and size of the families in Talipusngo and Layong Mabilog.

Table 1. Family Structure of Talipusngo and Layong Mabilog Community

Family Structure	Talipusngo (N = 69)		Layong Mabilog (N=71)		
	F	%	F	%	
Family Type	Nuclear	51	74	49	69
	Extended	18	26	22	31
Authority	Patriarchal	26	38	28	39
	Matriarchal	21	30	16	23
	Egalitarian	18	26	19	27
	Matricentric	4	6	8	11
Family Size	1-3 children	28	41	35	49
	4-6 children	31	45	23	32
	7-10 children	6	8	7	10
	More than 10 children	4	6	6	9

As seen in Table 1, most households in Barangay Talipusngo have a nuclear family structure (74%), and twenty-six (26%) have extended families. The same is true for Barangay Layong Mabilog, where 69% have nuclear families and 31% have extended families. During the survey, though, the team found out that there are two or three families in one house. They are usually the married sons or daughters who are still living in their parents' homes and contribute to family support. Other members of the extended family, such as grandparents, aunts, uncles, or cousins, share a home and play significant roles.

As to authority, 38% are patriarchal for Talipusngo and 39% for Layong Mabilog. This type of social structure exists in the Philippines, where the father is the head of the family, clan, or tribe, and children are considered to be inherited from him through the male line.

As to the family size, in Talipusngo, forty-one percent (41%) of the respondents have four to six children, followed by 41% with one to three children, then eight percent (8%) have seven to ten children, and six percent (6%) have more than ten children. In Layong Mabilog, forty-nine percent (49%) have one to three children, followed by thirty-two percent (32%) with four to six children, ten percent (10%) with seven to 10 children, and nine percent (9%) with more than 10 children. Based on the interviews conducted among the respondents, with the large number of family members, it is hard to provide even for the food alone. In fact, they encounter difficulty sending most children to school due to financial constraints.

1.2. Length of Residency

The length of the residency profile refers to the number of years of stay of the members of the community in the barangays. Table 2 shows the length of the residency profile of Barangays Talipusngo and Layong Mabilog.

Table 2. Length of Residency Profile of Barangays Talipusngo and Layong Mabilog Community

Length of Residency	Talipusngo (N = 69)		Layong Mabilog (N=71)	
	F	%	F	%
0-1 year	2	3	2	3
2-5 years	11	16	15	21
6-10 years	7	10	10	14
11-15 years	6	9	9	13
16-20 years	9	13	3	4
21-25 years	7	10	1	1
26 years and above	27	40	31	44

Findings revealed that a higher percentage of respondents have been living in their respective barangays for more than 26 years. The length of residence may encourage the development of patterns of interactions, including social networks and social support.

1.3. Socio-economic Profile

Socio-economic profile refers to the educational attainment, employment of the members of the family, and their average combined monthly income. Table 3 shows the socio-economic profile of Barangays Talipusngo and Layong Mabilog. As seen in the table, in Barangay Talipusngo, fifty-one percent (51%) reached elementary school level; forty-two percent (42%) earned high school education; and seven percent (7%) were able to reach college. In Barangay Layong Mabilog, fifty-three percent (53%) reached elementary school level; forty-one percent (41%) earned high school education; and six percent (6%) were able to reach college.

Findings revealed that most residents of both barangays only acquired basic education, which hinders them from finding employment and jobs other than farming, stick making, fishing, fish vending, labor, and owning small retail stores. As shown in Table 3, only 7% from Talipusngo and 6% from Layong Mabilog were professionals.

On the combined monthly income of the households in Talipusngo, sixty-seven percent (67%) earns about Php 5,000 and below; twenty-two percent (22%) earns between Php 5,001 and 10,000; three percent (3%) earns from Php 10,001 to 15,000; seven percent (7%) earns between Php 15,001 and 20,000; and one percent (1%) earns more than Php 20,001. In Layong Mabilog, sixty-two percent (62%) earns about Php 5,000 and below; twenty-one percent (21%) earns between Php 5,001 and 10,000; four percent (4%) earns between Php 10,001 and 15,000; eight percent (8%) earns between Php 15,001 and 20,000; and five percent (5%) earns more than Php 20,001.

According to Bacudan-Dacuycuy and Lim (2013), the government places greater focus on eradicating chronic poverty because it makes up a larger percentage of all forms of poverty. Researchers suggested that social safety nets be created to focus on negative impacts in the labor market. In addition, the government has to guarantee school advancement in addition to providing universal primary education, particularly in rural areas where rates of chronic poverty are higher.

Table 3. Socio-economic Profile of Barangays Talipusngo and Layong Mabilog Community

Socio-Economic Profile	Talipusngo (N = 69)		Layong Mabilog (N=71)		
	F	%	F	%	
Educational Attainment	Elementary	35	51	38	53
	High School	29	42	29	41
	College	5	7	4	6
Employment	Employed	26	37	52	38
	Unemployed	38	55	47	35
	Self-employed	5	8	36	27
Source of Income	Farming	18	26	20	28
	Stick making	15	22	9	13
	Fishing	10	14	18	25
	Fish vending	6	8	9	13
	Laborer	12	17	11	16
	Small retail store owner	8	12	4	6
Combined Family Income	P5,000 and below	46	67	44	62
	P5,001-10,000	15	22	15	21
	P10,001-15,000	2	3	3	4
	P15,001-20,000	5	7	6	8

The Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA) published data on poverty among families in 2013, which is an important socioeconomic indicator that influences policymakers' efforts to reduce poverty. The Food and Nutrition Research Institute (FNRI) defines the food threshold as the minimal income necessary to meet one's vital nutritional demands and meet basic food needs to maintain one's economic and social productivity. It is performed to assess extreme or surviving poverty. A related concept is the "poverty threshold," which is extended to cover necessities other than food, like clothing, housing, transportation, healthcare, and educational costs (Official Gazette, 2014).

Considering the combined income of the family as against the family expenditures, more than 60% in both barangays are poor, as indicated in the PSA report. Generally, findings revealed that most residents of Talipusngo and Layong Mabilog have only earned basic education and are poor based on the poverty threshold in 2013. For instance, according to the National Statistical Coordination Board (NSCB), a family of five had at least Php 5,590 on average per month to cover their basic food needs during the first semester of 2013, and at least Php 8,022 on average every month to cover both basic food and non-food needs. The monthly food threshold and the monthly poverty threshold are represented by these amounts, respectively (Official Gazette, 2014). Orbeta (2006) recommended targeting poor households, particularly those with large family sizes, to determine the regressiveness of the impact of additional children within families.

1.4. Home and Environment Profile

Home and environment profiles refer to house and lot ownership, type of house, and cleanliness inside and outside their homes. Table 4 shows the home and environment profiles of the residents of Barangays Talipusngo and Layong Mabilog.

Table 4. Home Ownership and Environment Profile

Home Ownership and Environment Profile		Talipusngo (N = 69)		Layong Mabilog (N=71)	
		F	%	F	%
House and Lot Ownership	Owned	58	84	57	80
	Rented	3	4	0	0
	Lived as tenants	8	12	14	20
Housing Materials	Concrete (Strong)	33	48	27	38
	Wood and Concrete (Mixed)	19	28	33	47
	Light Concrete and Wood	16	23	11	15
	Makeshift / Nipa Hut	1	1	0	0
Housing Adequacy	Adequate	57	83	52	73
	Inadequate	12	17	19	27
Home Ventilation Adequacy	Adequate	59	86	58	82
	Inadequate	10	14	13	18
Types of Toilet Facilities	Level 1 – Pit Latrines (dry toilet system)	39	57	36	51
	Level 2 – Poured	29	42	32	45
	Level 3 – Flushed	1	1	3	4
Ownership of the Toilet Facilities	Private	56	81	60	85
	Communal	6	9	5	7
	Shared	7	10	6	8
Source of Water Supply	Level 1 – Point Source (protected well or developed spring)	21	30	31	44
	Level 2 – communal source (reservoir, a piped distribution network and communal faucet)	15	22	11	15
	Level 3 – individual house connection	33	48	29	41

In terms of house and lot ownership, in Talipusngo, 84% of the respondents claimed to own their houses and lots, while 4% claimed they were only renting, and 12% claimed they were allowed to live free or as tenants.

In Layong Mabilog, 80% of the respondents claimed to own their houses and lots, while 20% claimed they were allowed to live free or as tenants or caretakers.

As to the type of houses or housing materials used, in Talipusngo, 48% have concrete houses, 28% have houses made of concrete and wood, 23% are made of light concrete and wood, and 1% own a makeshift house or nipa hut. In Layong Mabilog, 47% have mixed concrete-wood houses, 38% have houses made of concrete, 15% are made of light concrete and wood, and nobody owns a makeshift house or nipa hut.

As to the adequacy of living space, 83% of the respondents from Talipusngo claimed that they have adequate space, and 17% claimed that the space is inadequate. In Layong Mabilog, 73% claimed adequate, with 23% claiming inadequate space for living. Adequacy of space is very important in relation to the number of people staying in one house, especially for the health and well-being of the members of the family. The health effects of exposure to temperature extremes, which are happening more frequently as a result of climate change, can be made worse by inadequate housing or living circumstances (Rosidi et al., 2020). Significant health concerns associated with housing include the transmission of infectious diseases from unsafe living conditions, the risk of home injuries from confined spaces, and disorders of the heart and lungs from indoor air pollution (WHO, 2018). Al-Homoud (2003) considered housing gateways, open spaces, the number of floors, corridors, and housing unit floor areas as part of an engaging and socially stimulating environment and also for strengthening the healthy lives of those residents in the community.

As to ventilation, in Talipusngo, 86% claimed that they have adequate ventilation, while only 14% claimed inadequate ventilation. In Layong Mabilog, 82% claimed adequacy of ventilation, with 16% who claimed inadequate. An interior space that is warm, healthy, and productive must have adequate ventilation. Inadequate ventilation contributes to the development of allergies and asthma by increasing the risk of airborne infectious disease transmission, indoor pollution buildup, and moisture (WHO, 2018).

As to the types of toilet facilities, both respondents from Talipusngo and Layong Mabilog claimed more than 50% used the pit latrines. While very few had flushed toilets among the residents, As to ownership of the toilets, 81% from Talipusngo and 85% from Layong Mabilog privately owned their toilet facilities. The pit latrine is one of the most common, cheapest, and most improved forms of human excreta disposal. Low-income nations use these systems to expand access to better sanitation and reduce the prevalence of open defecation (Graham & Polizzotto, 2013). As to source of water supply, in Talipusngo, 48% had an individual house connection, while in Layong Mabilog, 44% had a point source (a protected well or developed spring) as their primary source of water supply.

However, the risk of groundwater contamination and health risks associated with pit latrines is high. In a study by Ndoziya et al. (2019), groundwater sources were more likely to be contaminated since elements like nitrates, chlorides, and ammonia contributed more to the water samples exceeding the recommended levels in drinking water.

1.5. Health Profile

A community health profile is a compilation of data regarding the demographics of the community, the resources available for health, the community's overall health perception, and the availability of employment (Jack & Holt, 2008). Table 5 shows the community health profile of Barangays Talipusngo and Layong Mabilog.

Table 5. Community Health Profile of Barangays Talipusngo and Layong Mabilog

Community Health Profile		Talipusngo (N = 69)		Layong Mabilog (N=71)	
		F	%	F	%
Health Resources / Facilities within the Community	Barangay Health Center	26	38	25	35
	Hospital	0	0	1	1
	Clinics	43	62	45	64
Availability of Health Insurance	With Insurance Coverage	36	52	38	53
	No Insurance Coverage	33	48	33	47
Practice Family Planning	Yes	41	59	29	41
	No	28	41	42	59
Facilities / Person Consulted in Case of Illness	Private Hospital	19	28	23	32
	Government Hospital	19	28	21	30
	Barangay Health Center	30	43	18	25
	Albularyo (Faith healer)	1	1	7	10
	Hilot (Midwife)	0	0	2	3
Prenatal Check-up Consultation	Health center	32	67	35	72
	Private doctor	4	8	10	20
	Midwife	11	23	4	8
	Others	1	2	0	0

As shown, respondents from Barangays Talipusngo and Layong Mabilog claimed the existence and availability of clinics with 62% and 64%, followed by the health center and the absence of hospitals according to respondents from Talipusngo but with 1% availability from Layong Mabilog respondents. As to the availability of health insurance, more than 50% of both barangays have insurance coverage. These imply that they are aware of the importance of health insurance primarily for their personal peace of mind when a member of the family is afflicted with illness.

As to family planning practices, in Talipusngo, 59% practice family planning, whereas in Layong Mabilog, 59% do not practice family planning. In cases of illness, respondents from Talipusngo claimed that they consulted the barangay health center (43%) more than the private and government hospitals. In Layong Mabilog, they consult more private hospitals (32%) than government hospitals and barangay health centers.

For pregnant women, respondents from Talipusngo (67%) and Layong Mabilog (72%) consulted the barangay health center more than other practitioners. These results show that they trusted their health center's manpower in the provision of prenatal services.

Shahidi et al. (2015) suggested that it is feasible to improve the health and well-being of the community by implementing a healthcare system that relies on practical strategies to resolve previous issues with inequities, cultural barriers, and poor communication, including a lack of resources, access to services, and mistrust of outsiders. Within their own communities, these indigenous groups come together to effectively promote health, help with medical guidance, and investigate the healthcare system.

2. Existing Conditions of Barangays Talipusngo and Layong Mabilog Community

In assessing the existing conditions of the community residents, some of the guide questions required multiple responses; hence, the percentage distribution could not be properly determined. Table 6 shows a summary of the existing conditions of the members of the community in Barangays Talipusngo and Layong Mabilog.

Table 6. Summary of the Existing Conditions of Barangays Talipusngo and Layong Mabilog Community

Existing Conditions		Talipusngo (N = 69)		Layong Mabilog (N=71)	
		F	%	F	%
Environment and Sanitation					
Solid Waste Disposal (Garbage)	Recycling (segregated)	14	20	24	34
	Not segregated	11	16	10	14
	Burning	32	47	23	32
	Open dumping	11	16	12	17
	Throwing in the river	0	0	2	3
	Sorting / grinding	0	0	0	0
	Animal feeding	1	1	0	0
Social Indices					
Knowledge / awareness about organization	Yes	39	57	45	63
	No	30	43	26	37
Awareness of activities and projects	Yes	37	54	34	48
	No	32	46	37	52
Involvement in activities	Involved (attending meetings, planning, and implementation)	36	52	31	44
	Not involved	33	48	40	56
Membership in Organization	Yes	20	29	22	31
	No	49	71	49	69

Problem Coping / Solving Capability					
Family participation	Yes	59	86	58	82
	No	10	14	13	18
Needs assistance from relatives	Yes	38	55	43	61
	No	31	45	28	39
Needs assistance from others (social workers)	Yes	30	43	41	58
	No	39	57	30	42
Means of communication	Cellphone	67	98	70	99
	Telephone	1	1	0	0
	E-mails	0	0	1	1
	Letters	1	1	0	0
	Lighting source	Electric	57	83	65
	Kerosene	12	17	6	8
Family status for the last five years	A lot improved	12	17	8	11
	Better than before	19	28	35	49
	Same as usual	26	38	21	30
	Worse than before	11	16	7	10
	A lot worse than before	1	1	0	0

As shown, 47% of the residents of Talipusngo resort to burning as their mode of garbage disposal. What is notable is that the residents do not throw their garbage into the nearby river, which is a good practice to prevent polluting the river. They do not sort or grind their garbage. In Layong Mabilog, on the other hand, the residents recycled or segregated their garbage (34%), although 32% of them also resorted to burning their garbage. Three (3) percent claimed that from time to time they throw their garbage on the river, although they changed their habit to prevent pollution.

In terms of social indices, in Talipusngo, 53% are aware of the presence of an organization; 54% are aware of the activities implemented by these organizations, like those of the Pantawid Familyang Pilipino Program (4Ps) and the Department of Health; 52% are involved; but 71% are not members of these organizations. In Layong Mabilog, 63% are aware of the existence of an organization, such as the Department of Health; hence, they are encouraged to avail of the programs. More than 52%, however, are not aware of the activities going on, such as those of solid waste management. What is ironic is that the barangay has a material recovery facility; perhaps more effort should be exerted by the barangay to ensure that efforts toward environmental sanitation are disseminated. Fifty-six (56%) percent are not involved in activities implemented, and 69% are not members.

In terms of the coping or problem-solving capability of the residents, 86% from Talipusngo and 82% from Layong Mabilog claimed that they actively participate in solving family problems. When it comes to problems within the confines of the home, they are still the members of the family who will resolve conflicts, disagreements, or even the most critical problems that may arise. Although there are those who seek assistance from relatives (55% and 61%, respectively), others opt to seek assistance from social workers from time to time.

Regarding the means of communication, the use of cellular phones was rated as the highest, with 98% from Talipusngo and 99% from Layong Mabilog. The results are a plus factor for the residents because, in any circumstance, they could be located since communication is not a problem. As for the source of lighting, 83% from Talipusngo and 92% from Layong Mabilog claimed that the major source of their lighting is electric, while a few still claimed that their sources are the use of kerosene.

As to their family status, in Talipusngo, 38% claimed that their family status is the same as before: 28% better than before; 12% a lot improved; 11% worse than before; and 1% a lot worse than before. In Layong Mabilog, 49% claimed that their status is far better than before, while nobody claimed that they are a lot worse than before. Some answers are: 11% a lot improved; 30% same as before; and 10% worse than before.

In a related study by Blay et al. (2015), the built environment is significantly related to health-related behaviors, with more adverse built environmental characteristics and more harmful or less protective health-related behaviors. In addition, little community participation in publicly initiated projects and a lack of adaptation funding for community-based strategies were identified as challenges to implementing solutions for communities, especially those involving climate resilience (Jamero et al., 2018).

3. Needs of Community Residents

The respondents were asked about their needs in the community. Findings are shown in Table 7.

Table 7. Community Needs of Talipusngo and Layong Mabilog Communities

Community Needs	Talipusngo (N = 69)		Layong Mabilog (N=71)	
	F	%	F	%
Food	53	77	43	61
Health	23	33	21	30
Education	23	33	22	31
Clothing	27	39	19	27
Financial Support	19	28	24	33
<i>*Multiple responses</i>				

Table 7 reflects the needs of the community. As seen, the highest need of the respondents from Talipusngo is food (77%), followed by clothing (39%; health and education (both of the same percentage), and financial (28%. Respondents from Layong Mabilog rated food as the highest, at 61%, followed by financial support at 33%, education at 31%, health at 30%, and clothing at 27%. Looking at the ratings, the residents give priority to food as one of their top needs.

Purdam et al. (2016) highlighted issues of food insecurity, which can be related to aspects of identity among families and households. They added that social isolation contributes to this issue for parents in terms of friendships and other relationships with children. Another study by Tankard and Paluck (2016) believed that a measurement of perceived norms should be more consistently integrated into social interventions focusing on institutional change.

Further research on institutional or policy changes is essential to further understand how new laws and programs affect the social norms of individuals.

4. Problems of the Community

Problems refer to the difficulties encountered by the households based on the survey and interviews among the respondents. Table 8 shows the problems that the respondents expressed they have encountered with their family members.

Table 8. Household Problems

Household Problems		Talipusngo (N = 69)		Layong Mabilog (N=71)	
		F	%	F	%
Family-Related	Financial	30	43.4	31	43.7
	Education	12	17.3	3	4.2
	Food	10	14.4	9	12.7
	Health (Pregnancy = 1)	5	7.24	11	14.1
	Work	5	7.24	8	11.3
	House	1	1.4	2	2.8
	Friends	0	0	1	1.4
	Gossip	0	0	1	1.4
	Electricity and water	1	1.4	1	1.4
	Internal family problems	5	7.24	3	4.2
Community- Related	Garbage	28	40.6	3	4.2
	Water system	3	4.34	10	14
	No employment opportunity (work)	3	4.34	3	4.2
	Road	1	1.4	31	42.3
	Farm	1	1.4	7	10
	Electricity	3	4.34	2	3
	Insects / pests / animals	10	14.44	8	11.2
	Transportation	2	2.89	2	3
	Food	3	4.34	1	1
	Flood	0	0	1	1
	Street lights	12	17.39	3	4.2
	Drainage	1	1.4	0	0
	Patrol	1	1.4	0	0
	Other (Gossip)	1	1.4	1	1

As shown, respondents from Talipusngo identified the following family-related problems: financial (43.4%), followed by education (17.3%), and food (14.4%). For Layong Mabilog respondents, they identified the following family-related problems: financial (43.7), followed by health (14.1), food (12.7), and work (11.3%). As to the community-related problems, respondents from Talipusngo include garbage, 40.6%; street lights, 17.39; and insects, pests, and animals, 14.44%. Respondents from Layong Mabilog identified the following community-related problems: road, 42.3%; water system, 14%; insects, pests, and animals, 11.2%; and farm, 10%.

It can be said that the main problems of the Barangay Talipusngo and Layong Mabilog respondents were identified in terms of the resilience of the community. Given the status of the different communities, Llenares and Deocar (2018) implied that the institutions should implement programs containing active responsiveness and community empowerment through the actions of the delivering institution in association with the approaches of the stakeholders for a more sustainable, developing community.

5. Proposed programs or activities to include in the five-year development plan

Based on the findings, the researchers suggest the following programs or activities for their outreach services:

1. Livelihood programs will help the community members augment their meager income. Since there are crops available, like cassava, bananas, and other produce, the residents could turn these into businesses.
2. Literacy programs could be designed to train out-of-school youth and other segments in need of services such as computer literacy and numeracy skills for schoolchildren, and home-based learning activities by training parents.
3. Awareness for environmental protection and management will show the residents how to keep their surroundings clean, green, and safe for healthy living.
4. Health education could include disease prevention tips, knowledge of communicable diseases, family planning, the Tuberculosis-Directly Observed Therapy Shortcourse (TB-DOTS), child rearing tips, and others that will prevent communicable diseases from spreading in the community. Health workers could be invited to the place for health information dissemination.
5. Social development skill trainings, activities, and programs that will improve an individual's social relations or boost their confidence while working in small teams or groups.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. Barangays Talipusngo and Layong Mabilog comprise households that are mostly nuclear and are composed of families with more than three or four children each. In addition, in terms of authority, most are patriarchal. Most of the residents had been in their respective barangays for more than 26 years. In addition, most of the community members only acquired basic education, and most families are considered poor considering their small income.

Moreover, most of the community members owned their houses, which were mostly made of concrete or mixed (concrete-wood) materials. They have health center facilities that are fully utilized for maternal and child care.

- Most of the members of the community in both barangays have their own individual water supply. In Talipusngo, the majority disposed of their garbage by burning, while in Layong Mabilog, they segregated and recycled their solid waste. For sewerage and waste water disposal, the majority used pit latrine types. Most of the members of the community are aware of the existence of an organization, and they are involved. Communication is not a problem since almost a 100 percent rating was given by the respondents. As for their family status, they claimed that their status was the same as usual.
- Members of the community identified food as their primary need, followed by financial needs, education, health, and clothing.
- Family-related problems are mostly financial in nature. Community-related problems include garbage, roads, and water systems, including insects, pests, and animals.
- Proposed programs or activities for outreach must include livelihood programs, literacy, health prevention management, and environmental protection and management.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following statements are recommended:

- Barangay leaders and stakeholders from St. Dominic College of Asia must plan and implement steps to address the needs and problems of the community. Higher education institutions must include the needs and problems identified in this study as components of their outreach programs.
- Households have to be resourceful. They could have backyard gardening to have a source of food as well as augment their income by selling their produce, such as fruits and vegetables.
- The members of the community have to be vigilant about cleanliness and sanitation to eradicate insects or pests because a dirty environment is a source of illness.

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